

ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE OF AND ATTITUDES TOWARDS CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING AMONG UNIVERSITY OF JOS FEMALE UNDERGRADUATES

Gimba¹, Solomon Musa, Emmanuel¹, Andy, Afoi, Barry Baidi²., Mangai¹, Mafuyai Joseph and Bukuta, Godiya
¹Department of Nursing Science, Faculty of Medical Sciences, University of Jos. ²College of Nursing and Midwifery, Kafanchan.

ABSTRACT

Cervical cancer screening has been reported by several researchers to influence the incidence and prognosis of cancer. The knowledge of people towards this screening have been said to influence attitudes towards practice. The researchers therefore sort to assess the knowledge and attitudes of the student population in the University of Jos. A sample size of 120 was selected from the population of study. A descriptive survey design was used to assess the knowledge and attitudes of respondents and the findings were illustrated and interpreted using descriptive and inferential statistics. The researchers among other findings found out that only 33.04% have ever heard of Pap smear, among which only about 55.10% related it cervical cancer. Only 7.89% knew the recommended age for the screening and only 10.53% were aware of the frequency. About 53.04% felt that the test is relevant to them. Also 50.50% intend to do the test. About 63.63% said lack of knowledge about the test is the reason for not practicing Pap smear. The findings indicate that even though the respondents' knowledge was grossly inadequate, the respondents showed positive attitudes towards the test. The relationship between knowledge and attitude was significant, indicating that their knowledge did influence their attitude towards cervical cancer screening.

KEYWORDS: cervical cancer, Pap smear, undergraduate female students, knowledge and attitude.

Received for Publication: 23/01/14

Accepted for Publication: 20/03/14

Corresponding Author: kingimba@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

The disease represents a unique public health opportunity unlike other cancers, it is preventable when detected and treated at an early; otherwise, it is almost always fatal (Alliance for Cervical Cancer Prevention (ACCP), 2004). While a woman in the United States has a 70% chance of surviving cervical cancer, the chance is reduced to 58% in Thailand, 42% in India, and 21% in Sub-Saharan Africa (Bishop, Wells, Sherris, Tsu and Crook, 1995).

In high income countries, the availability of cervical screening programs and treatment in a wide variety of service delivery channels has drastically reduced the incidence of cervical cancer, contrasting that of developing countries where up to 80% of the estimated 280 thousand annual deaths from the disease worldwide occurs as a result of very few programs offering relatively comprehensive screening (Sherris, Wells, Tsu and Crook, 1993).

According to American Cancer Society (ACS), (2011), all women should begin cervical cancer screening about 3 years after they begin having vaginal intercourse but no later than 21 years of age. Screening should be done every year with the regular Pap test or every 2 years using the newer liquid based Pap test. Beginning at age 30, women who have had three (3) normal Pap test results in a row may get screened every 2-3 years. Women older than 30 years may also get screened every three (3) years with either the conventional or liquid bases Pap test, plus HPV

test. However, doctors may suggest woman gets screened more often if she has certain risk factors, such as HPV infection, HIV infection, or a weak immune system, as the disease is more likely to progress faster in such individuals. Women 70 years of age or older, who have had 3 or more Pap test in a row and no abnormal Pap test in the last 10 years may choose to stop having Pap test. Also, women who have had a total hysterectomy done may also choose to stop having Pap test, unless the surgery was done as a treatment for cervical cancer or pre-cancer.

The test can help to prevent 75% out of every 100 cervical cancers from developing. It is the best way to detect changes that lead to cervical cancer as almost half of the women who develop cervical cancer in the United Kingdom have never had cervical screening test (BHIT, 2011).

Breikopt, *et al* (2005) posits that though women may be aware that they should be screened, they may lack the basic understanding of the process, limitation and results of the Pap test. Thus, the more knowledgeable women are about Pap test, the more likely they are to make screening visits and adhere to recommended follow-up for an abnormal result (Dignam, *et al*, 1996).

An Australian study of cervical screening barriers found poor cervical screening knowledge despite women's command of the medical terminology. Women who have had a Pap smear or heard of the test failed to realize that it was a cervical cancer screening procedure. In the same study, women exhibited inability to differentiate between cervical cancer screening and other diagnostic tests. The women, who knew of the existence of Pap smear or had had one, did not necessarily distinguish between the screening and other diagnostic tests. This indicates that their knowledge is poor (Markovic, Kesic, Topic and Matejick, 2005).

In a study of some American adolescent patients' understanding of Pap smear, remarkably few patients who participated in the study understood the meaning of the term Pap smear. More than two-third believed that Pap smear was synonymous to pelvic examination (Fletcher and Bryden, 2005). In a study in Southern Illinois in which women with abnormal screening cervical cytology attending University colposcopy clinics were asked about knowledge of Pap testing, only 131 (74%) of the respondents understood that Pap tests evaluate the cervix, whereas 137 (78%) understood that Pap test should be repeated at intervals of 1-3 years (Massad *et al*, 2006). A study in Germany on breast and cervical cancer screening participation, motivation and knowledge of the risk factors, 69.9% considered themselves insufficiently informed on the risk factors of cervical cancer (Klug *et al*, 2005).

A questionnaire was distributed to female undergraduates in South-Western Ontario, Canada, and was examined; preliminary analysis revealed that women who had received a Pap test were more knowledgeable about cervical health than those who had not; however, overall knowledge of among all the women was inadequate. One of the disconcerting findings was that overall, the women regardless of Pap smear status, were not knowledgeable about their cervical health. Although women who had Pap smears were more knowledgeable about their cervical health, their knowledge was still inadequate despite the fact that 82% of the women reported themselves to be knowledgeable about Pap smear. 55.3% (n=88) of the women reported having had a Pap test, with less than 10% of the women having the test 2 or less years prior to the study (Fletcher and Brayden, 2005).

A cross sectional study was carried out using a self-administered questionnaires, among four (4) different groups of well educated women in the University of Ghana main and medical campuses in Accra, Ghana. These groups were medical students, non-medical undergraduate students, nurses, and senior university workers. 164 (93%) Of the respondents had heard of cervical cancer, but only 65 (37%) had adequate knowledge, nurses and medical students were significantly in the majority. Only 68 respondents (39%) had sufficient knowledge about Pap smear, with only 15 respondents (8.5%) reporting to have ever had a Pap test done. 114 respondents (65%) had never gone for a general check-up, but 141 (80%) of them went to the hospital when they fall sick (Adanu, 2002).

In a cross-sectional study in Owerri, South-Eastern Nigeria, low levels of awareness of cervical cancer and screening was reported. 52.8% for awareness and only 7.1% had ever done the test (Ezem, 2007).

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Despite the existence of evidence-based secondary prevention methods such as Pap smear, cervical cancer kills a disproportionate number of women in developing countries (ACCP, 2004). With the test requiring repeated or routine screenings of women at intervals, developing countries may not have prowess to carry out this model, and as such, may not have the capacity for their health services to organize and sustain such programs.

This study therefore, seeks to assess the female students' awareness and attitude towards cervical screening, as well as proffer relevant findings and recommendations that will help in curbing the menace posed by cervical cancer.

OBJECTIVES

Specific objectives include to;

1. Assess the respondents' knowledge of cervical cancer screening.
2. Find out the female undergraduates' attitude towards cervical screening (Pap smear).

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study will provide the respondents as well as women in general, with an insight on cervical cancer; its screening techniques and the benefits of early diagnoses, which when coupled with skillful and respectful provision of such services will increase their propensity of utilizing as well as recommending the screening to their friends and family.

As an adjunct, findings from this study is intended towards adding to the body of knowledge, which as a consequence, will sensitize policy makers on the need to devise a means of relating such information to women, with the view of creating awareness, creating positive attitude in them, which could increase utilization of such services. It also seeks to make necessary suggestion and recommendations relevant to increasing the availability, access and willingness of respondents, and broadly women, on the utilization of cervical screening services. It will also provide information that will serve as an avenue for further research.

SCOPE AND LIMITATION OF STUDY

This study will be conducted in University of Jos, Jos, Plateau State, and covers only the female undergraduates of the institution. The research is restricted to University of Jos' female undergraduates due to brevity of time and financial constraints, and as such, generalization beyond this confine will have to be done with utmost caution.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

It is a quantitative research based on the classification made by Robson in 1993. In more specific terms, the study is a descriptive survey, a non-experimental study design which seeks to assess the female undergraduates' knowledge, attitude and practice of cervical cancer screening.

LOCATION/AREA OF STUDY

The study setting is University of Jos, situated in Jos North local government area of Plateau State, within the North-Central geo-political zone of the country.

The university was established in 1971 as a satellite campus of the University of Ibadan. In October 1975, the then military government under General Murtala Mohammed established the University as a separate institution. Existing faculties in the school include Arts and Social Sciences, Education, Environmental Sciences, Law, Management Sciences, Medical sciences, Natural Sciences, and Pharmaceutical Sciences. The University embraces 53

departments, a teaching hospital and several other academic units such as center for continuing education, center for research and development, the information and communication (ICT) directorate, among others.

The institution has two (2) campuses; the temporary site located along Bauchi road and the permanent site situated in Naraguta. The institution has student population as follows;

1. Full time students – 18, 952
2. Part time – 12, 389

The staff population is also as follows;

1. Academic staff – 871
2. Non-academic staff – 1,671

POPULATION OF STUDY

The population of study is the female undergraduates of the institution. This population comprises mainly of young adults who are in different levels of study at their various departments and faculties in the institution.

SAMPLE SIZE AND SAMPLING TECHINQUES

The study involved about 120 female undergraduates at different levels of study within the various faculties of the University. The method of sampling employed was convenience sampling, cutting across all the faculties of the institution.

INSTRUMENT FOR DATA COLLECTION

The instrument used for data collection was a semi structured questionnaire which was to be self-administered. Each respondent was asked to fill the questionnaire which is divided into three (3) sections; encompassing their socio-demographic characteristics, knowledge, as well as attitude and practice of cervical screening. The questions asked are simple and clear, and the rating scale used is Thurnstone scale.

RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY OF INSTRUMENT

The study adapted the structural format of an existing questionnaire whose psychometric properties have been established. Researchers proof read the questionnaire thoroughly individually and grey areas were addressed adequately. Pretesting was carried out on a small number of respondents as a trial run for the main research intended.

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

The instruments for data collection (questionnaire) were distributed to the respondents at their respective lecture halls, library, departmental spots or places of residence based on convenience. The researcher waited to collect the questionnaires from the respondents.

METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

The data provided by the respondents were processed and presented using the descriptive method of data analysis from which inferences were drawn. The information was represented using tables as well as frequency tables, percentages, measures of central tendencies. The inferential method was used to test the hypotheses of the research study.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Verbal informed consent was obtained from the respondents as regards participation in the study. Opting to participate was a choice as respondents were not coerced. To guarantee anonymity, questions eliciting the respondents' identity were avoided, and all the information provided by respondents was treated with utmost confidence. Also, the researcher attempted answering questions raised by respondents.

RESULTS**Table 1: Showing Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents**

Characteristics	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
AGE		
16-20	14	12.17
21-25	61	53.04
26-30	27	23.48
31-35	4	3.48
Above 35	5	4.35
No response	4	3.48
Total	115	100.00
FACULTY		
Arts	19	16.52
Education	14	12.17
Social science	16	13.91
Environmental science	8	6.96
Law	14	12.17
Management sciences	9	7.83
Medical sciences	19	16.52
Pharmacy	7	6.09
Natural science	8	6.96
No response	1	0.90
Total	115	100.00
LEVEL OF STUDY		
100	13	11.30
200	41	35.65
300	31	26.96
400	11	9.57
500	12	10.43
600	1	0.90
No response	6	5.22
Total	115	100.03

Tables 1 and 2 show that the mean age of respondents is approximately 24 years, with majority of the respondents; 61 (53.4%) falling within 21-25 years of age, and only a few; 5 (4.35%) being above 35 years of age. These respondents cut across the various faculties of the institution; with Faculties of Arts and Medical Sciences accounting for the highest percentages; 19 (16.52%) each, while pharmacy accounted for the least number of respondents; 7 (6.09%).

Most of the respondents are from 200 and 300 level; 41 (35.65%) and 31 (26.96%) respectively, while only 1 (0.90%) is from 600 level which could be attributable to the fact that only one department (medicine) has that level. Only few are married (11.30%, n=13), majority (86.96%, n=100) are single, while 2 of the respondents (1.74%) did not comment on their marital status. Of the married individuals, 11 (84.62%) are in a monogamous setting, while 1 (7.69%) is from a polygamous home. One did not comment on her type of marital setting.

Considering their system of belief, 108 (93.91%) of them are Christians, while 7 (6.09%) are Muslims, with none being traditional or from other religions of the world. In terms of ethnicity, it is indicative of the fact that those from other ethnic groups, aside the three major ethnic groups of the country, are in the majority; (57.39%, n=66). This is

Table 2: further showing the Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
MARITAL STATUS		
Married	13	11.30
Single	100	86.96
Separated/divorced	Nil	0.00
Widowed	Nil	0.00
No response	2	1.74
Total	115	100.00
TYPE OF MARRIAGE		
Monogamy	11	84.62
Polygamy	1	7.69
No response	1	7.69
Total	13	100.00
RELIGION		
Christianity	108	93.91
Islam	7	6.09
Others	Nil	0.00
Total	115	100.00
TRIBE		
Hausa	8	6.96
Igbo	23	20.00
Yoruba	13	11.30
Others	66	57.39
No response	5	4.35
Total	115	100.00

likely associated with the fact that other ethnic groups within the middle belt especially Plateau State, constitute the largest population of undergraduates of the institution.

Table 3 shows that more of the respondents; 63 (54.78%) are unaware of Pap smear test, with 38 (33.04%) indicating they have ever heard of the test, while 14 (12.17%) of them did not respond to the question.

Sampling from those that have ever heard of the test, 21 (37.50%) indicated health practitioners as their information source, with only 1 (1.79%) having a source other than the ones indicated in the questionnaire options/table (i.e. internet). Based on their personal description of Pap smear, 29 (76.32%) of the respondents commented, with about 16 (55.17%) of them relating the test to cervical cancer, while 10 (34.48%) of them were ambiguous as they only related it to the reproductive system (vagina to be specific). 2 (6.90%) related to cancer without any clear distinction. In addition, a reasonable number (44.74%, n=17) know that Pap smear is synonymous to cervical screening, with 15 (39.47%) misconceiving it to be vaginal examination, while 2 (5.26%) know nothing about its alternate name.

Table 3: Showing Knowledge of Pap smear Test

Questionnaire item	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Ever heard of pap smear		
Yes	38	33.04
No	63	54.78
No response	14	12.17
Total	115	99.99
Information source (multiple choice)		
Health practitioner	21	37.50
Friend/relation/colleague	10	17.86
Books/posters/magazine	8	14.29
Lecture/campaign	7	12.50
Media	7	12.50
others	1	1.79
no response	2	3.57
Total	56	100.01
Personal discrimination of pap smear		
Comments	29	76.32
No comments/response	9	23.68
Total	38	100.00
Based on comments made		
Relates to abdominal scan	1	3.45
Relates to reproductive organ	10	34.48
Relates to cancer without any clear cut distinction	2	6.90
Relates to cervical cancer	16	55.17
Total	29	100.00
Pap smear synonym		
Pelvic examination	2	5.26
Cervical screening	17	44.74
Vaginal examination	15	39.47
Don't know	2	5.26
No response	2	5.26
Total	38	99.99

Table 5 indicates that a greater proportion of the respondents; 19 (50%) thought that it is recommended for women as early as 18-21 years of age. Only 3 (7.89%) knew the recommended age for the first test, with 10 (26.32%) not knowing the recommended age. As regards the frequency of the test, only 4 (10.53%) are aware that the test is to be done once in every 2-3 years. 20 (52.63%) didn't know the recommended frequency of the test.

Tables 6 and 7 show that more than half of the respondents; 61 (53.04%) feel the test is relevant to them as individuals, with only 3 (2.61%) not seeing its relevance. A significant number also agree to allow a medical practitioner perform vaginal examination on them, even in the absence of any symptom, while 37 (32.17%) did not consent to it.

Table 4: Showing Respondents' Knowledge on Pap smear Recommendations

Questionnaire item	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Recommended early age for first pap smear test		
Below 18 years	5	13.16
18-21 years	19	50.00
22-30 years	3	7.89
31-40 years	Nil	-
Above 40 years	Nil	-
Don't know	10	26.32
No response	1	2.63
Total	38	100.00
Recommended pap smear frequency (years)		
Once a year	13	34.21
Once in 2-3 years	4	10.53
Once in 5 years	Nil	-
Once in 10 years	Nil	-
Don't know	20	52.63
No response	1	2.63
Total	38	100.00

Table 6: Showing Attitude towards Pap smear Test

Questionnaire item	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Feeling of the test relevance by respondents		
Yes	61	53.04
No	3	2.61
Don't know	33	28.70
No response	18	15.65
Total	115	100.00
Respondents' propensity to allow a medical practitioner perform vaginal examination in the absence of any symptom		
Yes	74	64.35
No	37	32.17
No response	4	3.48
Total	115	100.00
Intention of doing the test (for those who have never done the test)		
Not sure	23	23.23
Yes	50	50.50
No	14	14.14
No response	12	12.12
Total	99	99.99

Table 7: Further Showing Attitude towards Pap smear Test

Questionnaire item	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Reasons behind inability to have never done the test		
I have no knowledge about the test	63	63.63
I cannot afford it	3	3.03
My doctor has not requested	13	13.13
It is not necessary	6	6.06
I am afraid of a possible bad result	2	2.02
No response	12	12.12
Total	99	99.99
Consenting to pap smear test if given the opportunity		
Yes	82	71.30
No	5	4.35
Don't know	18	15.65
No response	10	8.70
Total	115	100.00

For those who have never done the test, about half of the population; 50 (50.50%) intend doing the test, while 14 (14.14%) are not intending on doing it. A greater number of them; 63 (63.63%), claim inadequate knowledge about the test as the reason behind their lack of practice, while 2 (2.02%) of them claim they are afraid of a possible bad result. Most of the respondents; 82 (71.30%) agree to do the test if given the opportunity, with only a few; 5 (4.35%) not consenting to it.

Table 8: Relationship between Knowledge and Attitude

Knowledge	Practice		Total
	Positive	Negative	
Yes	38(A)	0(B)	38
No	36(C)	41(D)	77
Total	74	41	115

Calculated $X^2 = 31.44$ $df=1$ $p=0.05$

Using non directional chi square table for $df=1$, level of significance = 0.05, critical value $=x^2\alpha = 3.84$. Since $x^2 > x^2\alpha$, H_0 is rejected while H_A is accepted, indicating that there is a significant relationship between knowledge and attitude among respondents.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

In this study, a significant number of the study population fell within the age range of 21-30 years. These respondents cut across the various Faculties of the Institution, with Faculties of Arts and Medical Sciences accounting for the highest percentages, while Pharmacy accounted for the least number of respondents. This is similar with the Canadian study on female undergraduates in south-Western Ontario as it cuts across the various faculties of the Institution (Fletcher, 2005).

Most of the respondents were from 200 and 300 level. Only few are married with the majority being single. Awareness of Pap smear test was below average, which is in contrast with high levels of awareness recorded among female university staff and students in Accra, Ghana (Adanu, 2002)

Respondents who were informed via health practitioners were more than those who got their information from lecture/campaign and media. More than half of the respondents were able to relate the test to cervical cancer, with a reasonable percentage relating it to the reproductive system. Just a few related the test to abdominal scan. This implies that less than half do not have a clear cut/distinctive knowledge of the test. This finding agrees with that of Massad *et al.*, (2006) but in contrast to that of a German study which indicated that more than half of the respondents considered themselves as insufficiently informed (Klug *et al.*, 2005). In addition, more than two-third of the respondents who demonstrated awareness on the test knew that Pap smear is synonymous to cervical screening. About half of the respondents said that the recommended age which the first Pap smear test should be done is 18-21 years. This is in line with the ACS's guidelines for the detection of cancer (2011), which states that all women should begin cervical cancer screening about 3 years after they begin having vaginal intercourse, but no later than 21 years old some. European countries also start at age 18.

Only a few knew that the recommended frequency for Pap smear test is every 2-3 years and a little below average of the respondents believed that Pap smear test should be done yearly. This belief is likely based on the previous WHO recommendation, however. However a little above average of the respondents didn't know how frequent the test is supposed to be done. This finding differs with that of Massad *et al.*, (2005) where majority of the respondents understood that Pap smear test should be repeated at intervals ranging from 1-3 years depending on result finding.

The study also revealed that more of the respondents have a supportive attitude towards testing despite the low knowledge about the test. This might be tied to their beliefs that all medical tests are beneficial and are geared towards maintaining an optimal health.

About half of those who have never done the test demonstrated their intention of doing the test. One of the respondents captured the researcher's attention as she indicated reason for saying no that she is a chosen, and as such, she will never get sick. This lays bare, the extent to which individuals can hold firmly to their belief and much effort will be put in order to convince such an individual to see the reasons for such screening programs.

Majority of the respondents consented to do the test if given the opportunity. The hypothesis tested revealed that there was a significant relationship between knowledge and attitude of respondents.

CONCLUSION

The study highlights the absence of adequate knowledge on cervical cancer screening among respondents. However, they have a positive attitude towards the screening, attributable to the general knowledge that individuals have regarding the significance of medical checkup.

REFERENCES

- Alliance for Cervical Cancer Prevention (ACCP) (2004). *Cervical cancer prevention issues; A systematic literature review*, Seattle: Author.
- American Cancer Society (ACS). (2011). *Guidelines for early detection of cancer*; Atlanta, GA: Author.
- Adanu, R. (2002). Cervical cancer knowledge and screening in Accra, Ghana. *Journal of Women's Health and Gender-based Medicine*, 11(6), 487.
- Breikopt, C., Pearson, H. and Breikopt, D. (2005). Poor knowledge regarding the pap test among low-income women undergoing routine screening. *Perspective on Sexual and Reproductive Health*, 37(2), 78-84.
- Bishop, A., Wells, E., Sherris, J., Tsu, V., and Crook, B. (1995). Cervical cancer; evolving prevention strategies for developing countries. *Reproductive Health Matters*, 6, 60-71.

Bupa's Health Information Team (BHIT) (2011). *Factsheet for women with cervical cancer*. United Kingdom: Author.

Dignam, M., Michielutte, R., Blinson, K., Wells, H., Case, L., and Sharp, P. (1996). Effectiveness of health education to increase screening for cervical cancer among eastern-band Cherokee Indian women in North Carolina. *Journal of the National Cancer Institute*, 88(22), 1670-1676.

Ezem, B. (2007). Awareness and uptake of cervical cancer screening in Owerri, South Eastern Nigeria. *Ann African Medical Journal*, 6(3), 94-98.

Fletcher, P. and Bryden, P. (2005). Preliminary examination of cervical health practices and knowledge among university-aged females. *College Students' Journal*, 39(3), 469.

Klug, S., Hetzer, M. and Bletner, M. (2005). Screening for breast and cervical cancer in a large German City: participation, motivation and knowledge of risk factors. *European Journal of Public Health*, 15(1), 70-77.

Markovic, M., Kesic, V., Topic, L. and Matejic, B. (2005). Barriers to screening: A qualitative study with women in Serbia. *Social Science and Medicine*, 61, 2528-2535.

Massad, L., Verhulst, S., Hagemeyer, M. and Brady, P. (2006). Knowledge of the cervical screening process among rural and urban Illinois women undergoing colposcopy. *Journal of Lower Genital Tract Disease*, 10(4), 252-255.

Sherris, J., Wells, E., Tsu, V. and Bishop, A. (1993). *Cervical cancer in developing countries: A situational analysis. Prepared for women's health and nutrition program series*. World Bank, Washington DC: World Bank.

